

Steroidal constituents of *Ailanthus excelsa* Roxb. (Simarubaceae)

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Ailanthus excelsa Roxb., a rich source of quassinoids and alkaloids, has yielded several steroidal constituents one of which is characterised as stigmasta-4,22-dien-3-one from comprehensive spectral analysis.

Ailanthus excelsa Roxb. (Simarubaceae) has been reported to possess antiviral, antitumour against P-388 lymphocytic leukaemia and cytotoxic activity against KB test system¹. It is also used for the cure of wounds and skin eruptions as mentioned in traditional medicine¹. From chemical point of view the plant is a rich source of quassinoids² and alkaloids³. The present study on the stem bark of the species resulted in the isolation of steroidal constituents, β -sitosterol and stigmasta-4,22-dien-3-one (1; AE-23).

The petrol extract of the stem bark of *A. excelsa* (5 kg) was chromatographed over silica gel column. The hexane-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluent furnished a solid, further purified by rechromatography. On rechromatography β -sitosterol and another steroidal compound, AE-23 were obtained. The latter was finally purified by preparative tlc (silica gel, E. Merck; the chromatogram was developed with hexane-ethyl acetate, 4 : 1 solvent system). Repeated crystallization from methanol yielded white shining needles of AE-23, m.p. 97°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +71.25^\circ$ (CHCl₃). AE-23 showed green colour with Libermann-Burchardt reagent. The compound exhibited uv-absorption bands at 243 and 225 nm (very low intensity). Ir absorption bands were found at 2930–2870, 1670 (conjugated CO), 1610 (double bond), 1440, 1120 and 770 cm⁻¹. ¹H nmr spectrum (300 MHz; CDCl₃) exhibited two olefinic protons (C₂₂-H and C₂₃-H) as two double doublets at δ 5.0 and 5.13 having J_1 9 Hz and J_2 15 Hz in each set. Other olefinic proton at C₄ resonated at δ 5.71 as a singlet. Remaining methyl, methylene and methine protons appeared

at δ 0.69–2.37 region. Characteristic cracking pattern was observed in mass spectrometry of the compound. M⁺ was found at m/z 410 and other fragments appeared at m/z 395, 271, 229, 146 and 124 (100%).

The structure of AE-23 received further support from the ¹³C nmr spectral analysis (Table 1). The environment of carbon was identified by APT spectrum. The assignments have been made from additivity relationship as well as by comparison with the model compounds⁴. The ¹³C nmr analysis was in consonance with the molecular architecture of stigmasta-4,22-dien-3-one.

Table 1. ¹³C nmr spectral data of stigmasta-4,22-dien-3-one (1) in CDCl₃ (75 MHz)

C	Chemical shift ppm	Nature of carbon in APT spectra
1	35.66	sp ³ -methylene
2	33.94	sp ³ -methylene
3	199.59	sp ² -quaternary
4	123.71	sp ² -tertiary
5	171.63	sp ² -quaternary
6	32.91 ^a	sp ³ -methylene
7	32.00 ^a	sp ³ -methylene
8	35.59	sp ³ -methine
9	53.79	sp ³ -methine
10	38.56	sp ³ -quaternary
11	20.98	sp ³ -methylene
12	39.59	sp ³ -methylene
13	42.24	sp ³ -quaternary
14	55.96	sp ³ -methine
15	24.15	sp ³ -methylene
16	28.82	sp ³ -methylene
17	55.85	sp ³ -methine
18	12.10 ^b	sp ³ -methyl
19	17.35	sp ³ -methyl

		<i>Table-1 (contd.)</i>
20	40.42	<i>sp</i> ³ -methine
21	21.25	<i>sp</i> ³ -methyl
22	138.15	<i>sp</i> ² -tertiary
23	129.42	<i>sp</i> ² -tertiary
24	51.19	<i>sp</i> ³ -methine
25	31.82	<i>sp</i> ³ -methine
26	21.11	<i>sp</i> ³ -methyl
27	19.00	<i>sp</i> ³ -methyl
28	25.35	<i>sp</i> ³ -methylene
29	12.20 ^b	<i>sp</i> ³ -methyl

^{a,b} Values are interchangeable.

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